

Spherical Fuzzy TOPSIS with Hybrid Entropy-FUCOM Weighting Method

Elif Güner¹, Başak Aldemir², Ebru Aydoğdu³, Halis Aygün¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Umuttepe Campus, 41380,
Kocaeli-TÜRKİYE

²Department of Mathematics, Afyon Kocatepe University, 03200,
Afyonkarahisar-TÜRKİYE

³Department of Basic Sciences, Naval Academy, Turkish National Defence University,
Istanbul-TÜRKİYE

Corresponding author: elif.guner@kocaeli.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-6969-400X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6969-400X)

Second Author: [0000-0002-9073-9364](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9073-9364)

Third Author: [0000-0002-2777-8651](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2777-8651)

Fourth Author: [0000-0003-3263-3884](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3263-3884)

DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.18017473](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18017473)

Abstract

In this study, a novel multi-criteria group decision-making method is developed by integrating subjective and objective weight determination within the framework of spherical fuzzy sets. In the proposed method, the weights of decision-makers are objectively determined by using an entropy measure function, while the criteria weights are calculated through a hybrid approach that combines the FUCOM and the entropy measure function. Thus, both subjective assessments (via FUCOM) and objective measures (via entropy) are simultaneously considered to determine the importance of the criteria. Then, this approach is integrated with the TOPSIS method in the spherical fuzzy environment. The proposed method provides a more balanced and consistent weighting system, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of different perspectives in decision-making processes. To demonstrate its applicability, the method is applied to a real-life problem. Moreover, several entropy measures from the literature are integrated into the proposed approach to perform a sensitivity analysis based on the obtained results. This analysis enables the evaluation of the method's performance and robustness under various conditions, providing an extensive comparison.

Keywords: [objective weighting], [subjective weighting], [entropy], [MCGDM]

1 Introduction

The theory of SFSs is a recent advancement in the field of fuzzy logic, designed to handle higher levels of uncertainty and imprecision in decision-making processes. Introduced in [8], SFSs extend traditional fuzzy sets by incorporating a three-dimensional membership structure that

includes a membership degree, a non-membership degree, and a neutral membership degree, all of which are constrained to the surface of a unit sphere. This innovative approach allows for a more comprehensive representation of uncertainty, making it particularly useful in complex decision-making environments where data may be incomplete, ambiguous, or imprecise. The primary advantage of SFSs lies in their ability to model and process a higher degree of uncertainty compared to traditional and even more advanced fuzzy set extensions such as intuitionistic fuzzy sets ([1]), picture fuzzy sets ([6]) and Pythagorean fuzzy sets ([12]). By ensuring that the sum of the squares of the membership, non-membership, and neutral-membership degrees equals one, SFSs provide a balanced and normalized framework for capturing the uncertainty inherent in many real-world problems. SFSs have been effectively integrated with various decision-making methods, enhancing their applicability and robustness in diverse scenarios. Among these methods, integrating SFSs with MCDM techniques such as TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) shows significant improvements in decision quality and robustness. The spherical fuzzy TOPSIS method allows for a more precise ranking of options by considering the complex uncertainty and imprecision associated with each criterion [8]. In the spherical fuzzy TOPSIS approach, the decision matrix is initially constructed using spherical fuzzy numbers to express the performance evaluations of each alternative with respect to each criterion. The spherical fuzzy decision matrix is then normalized so that all criteria become comparable. Subsequently, the weighted normalized decision matrix is obtained by incorporating the criteria weights, which may be determined subjectively through methods such as spherical fuzzy AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) or spherical fuzzy BWM (Best–Worst Method), and objectively through the entropy measure function ([3], [4]). Once the weighted evaluations are derived, the distances of the alternatives to the spherical fuzzy positive and negative ideal solutions are calculated, and the closeness coefficients are used to obtain the final ranking of the alternatives, thereby completing the spherical fuzzy TOPSIS procedure. In addition to these traditional weighting approaches, FUCOM (Full Consistency Method) has recently emerged as a subjective weighting technique that provides high precision and strong internal consistency. First introduced in [11], FUCOM addresses several limitations of methods such as AHP and BWM by enforcing a full consistency condition when comparing criteria. Because consistency plays a critical role in reliable decision-making, FUCOM ensures that all pairwise comparisons made by decision-makers (DMs) are fully transitive and logically coherent. This results in more accurate and dependable criteria weights.

In this study, we aim to combine entropy, FUCOM, and TOPSIS methods in SFSs to offer several significant advantages, particularly in decision-making and multi-criteria analysis. In this method, we calculate DMs weights using entropy, offering a solution for unknown DMs weights. We determine criterion weights both objectively and subjectively through entropy and the FUCOM method. To identify the best option, we apply the TOPSIS method after computing the criteria weights. Then, we apply the suggested method to the selection of digital market technology. Finally, we provide a sensitivity analysis by solving the problem using the other entropy measures for both the criterion and DM weights.

1.1 Preliminaries

This section presents some fundamental notions related to SFSs and existing entropy measure functions defined on SFSs.

Definition 1.1. [8] A SFS over the set of universe X is given by

$$S = \{ \langle x, \mu_S(x), \eta_S(x), \nu_S(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \} \quad (1)$$

where $\mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\mu_S^2(x) + \eta_S^2(x) + \nu_S^2(x) \leq 1$ for each $x \in X$. The values $\mu_S(x)$, $\eta_S(x)$ and $\nu_S(x)$ denote the positive-membership, neutral-membership and negative-membership of x to the set S , respectively. The refusal function is $\pi_S(x) = \sqrt{1 - \mu_S^2(x) - \eta_S^2(x) - \nu_S^2(x)}$ for every $x \in X$. We will denote the family of all SFSs over X as $\text{SFS}(X)$.

The complement of a SFS S is denoted by S^c and given as $S^c = \{ \langle x, \nu_S(x), \eta_S(x), \mu_S(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$.

Also, the triplet $S = (\mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S)$ is called a spherical fuzzy number (SFN) where $\mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S \in [0, 1]$ and $\mu_S^2 + \eta_S^2 + \nu_S^2 \leq 1$. We denote the collection of all SFNs by \mathcal{S} .

Definition 1.2. [8] Let $S = \langle \mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S \rangle$, $S_1 = \langle \mu_{S_1}, \eta_{S_1}, \nu_{S_1} \rangle$, $S_2 = \langle \mu_{S_2}, \eta_{S_2}, \nu_{S_2} \rangle$ be three SFNs and $k \geq 0$. Then the fundamental operations on SFNs are then given as follows:

- (i) $S_1 \leq S_2$ iff $\mu_{S_1} \leq \mu_{S_2}, \eta_{S_1} \leq \eta_{S_2}$ and $\nu_{S_1} \geq \nu_{S_2}$,
- (ii) $S_1 = S_2$ iff $S_1 \leq S_2$ and $S_2 \leq S_1$,
- (iii) $S_1 \oplus S_2 = \left(\sqrt{\mu_{S_1}^2 + \mu_{S_2}^2 - \mu_{S_1}^2 \mu_{S_2}^2}, \sqrt{(1 - \mu_{S_1}^2) \eta_{S_2}^2 + (1 - \mu_{S_2}^2) \eta_{S_1}^2 - \eta_{S_1}^2 \eta_{S_2}^2}, \nu_{S_1} \nu_{S_2} \right)$,
- (iv) $S_1 \otimes S_2 = \left(\mu_{S_1} \mu_{S_2}, \sqrt{(1 - \nu_{S_1}^2) \eta_{S_2}^2 + (1 - \nu_{S_2}^2) \eta_{S_1}^2 - \eta_{S_1}^2 \eta_{S_2}^2}, \sqrt{\nu_{S_1}^2 + \nu_{S_2}^2 - \nu_{S_1}^2 \nu_{S_2}^2} \right)$,
- (v) $kS = \left(\sqrt{1 - (1 - \mu_S^2)^k}, \sqrt{(1 - \mu_S^2)^k - (1 - \mu_S^2 - \eta_S^2)^k}, \nu_S^k \right)$,
- (vi) $S^k = \left(\mu_S^k, \sqrt{(1 - \nu_S^2)^k - (1 - \nu_S^2 - \eta_S^2)^k}, \sqrt{1 - (1 - \nu_S^2)^k} \right)$.

Definition 1.3. [7] Let $S, S_1, S_2 \in \mathcal{S}$ and $S = \langle \mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S \rangle$.

- (1) A logarithm-based score function $SF : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ is defined as

$$SF(S) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \mu_S^2 - \nu_S^2 - (\eta_S^2 + \pi_S^2) \frac{\log_2(1 + \eta_S^2 + \pi_S^2)}{100} \right).$$

- (2) An accuracy function $AF : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is given by $AF(S) = \mu_S^2 + \eta_S^2 + \nu_S^2$.

- (3) The ranking approach using score and accuracy functions proceeds as follows:

- (i) If $SF(S_1) < SF(S_2)$, then $S_1 \ll S_2$,
- (ii) If $SF(S_1) > SF(S_2)$, then $S_1 \gg S_2$,
- (iii) $SF(S_1) = SF(S_2)$, then
 - (a) $AF(S_1) < AF(S_2)$, then $S_1 \ll S_2$,
 - (b) $AF(S_1) > AF(S_2)$, then $S_1 \gg S_2$,
 - (c) $AF(S_1) = AF(S_2)$, then $S_1 = S_2$.

Next, we summarize some existing entropy measure functions given in SFS environment. Take $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ as the set of universe and $S = \{ \langle x_i, \mu_S(x_i), \eta_S(x_i), \nu_S(x_i) \rangle \mid x_i \in X, \forall i = \overline{1-n} \}$ as a SFS on X .

1. [5] gave the entropy measure function which is induced by generalized distance measure on SFSs and defined as follows:

$$E_B(S) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left((1 - d(S, S^c))^{\frac{1 + \pi_S^2(x_i)}{2}} \right)$$

where the mapping d on $SFS(X) \times SFS(X)$ is given by

$$d(S_1, S_2) = \left(\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_{S_1}^2(x_i) - \mu_{S_2}^2(x_i)|^\theta + |\eta_{S_1}^2(x_i) - \eta_{S_2}^2(x_i)|^\theta + |\nu_{S_1}^2(x_i) - \nu_{S_2}^2(x_i)|^\theta \right)^{\frac{1}{\theta}}.$$

For $\theta = 1$, the entropy measure function E_B is as follows:

$$E_B(S) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left((1 - |\mu_S^2(x_i) - \nu_S^2(x_i)|) \frac{2 - \mu_S^2(x_i) - \eta_S^2(x_i) - \nu_S^2(x_i)}{2} \right)$$

2. [9] presented an entropy measure function based on the logarithm function for SFSs:

$$E_J(S) = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\mu_S(x_i) \log(\mu_S(x_i)) + \eta_S(x_i) \log(\eta_S(x_i)) + \nu_S(x_i) \log(\nu_S(x_i)) \right).$$

3. [2] proposed a different entropy measure function for SFSs as follows:

$$E_{AG}(S) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{4}{5} (|\mu_S^2(x_i) - \nu_S^2(x_i)| + |\eta_S^2(x_i) - .25|) \right).$$

2 Methodology

Take $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$ as the set of n options, $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m\}$ the set of m criteria and $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_k\}$ the set of k DMs whose opinions are taken for decision-making process. Each DMs E_r ($1 \leq r \leq k$) evaluates the options A_p ($1 \leq p \leq n$) concerning C_q ($1 \leq q \leq m$) by considering the affect of C_q on the options A_p . The expert can use the nine-tuple linguistic term table shown in Table 1 when they attain a value for the options.

Table 1: Nine-tuple linguistic terms [8]

Linguistic terms	(μ_S, η_S, ν_S)
Absolutely low importance (ALI)	(0.1, 0.9, 0.1)
Absolutely more importance (AMI)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
Very high importance (VHI)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.2)
High importance (HI)	(0.7, 0.3, 0.3)
Slightly more importance (SMI)	(0.6, 0.4, 0.4)
Equally importance (EI)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)
Slightly low importance (SLI)	(0.4, 0.6, 0.4)
Low importance (LI)	(0.3, 0.7, 0.3)
Very low importance (VLI)	(0.2, 0.8, 0.2)

Then, they establish individually spherical fuzzy decision matrix (SFDM) $D^{(r)} = (d_{pq}^{(r)})_{n \times m}$ where $d_{pq}^{(r)} = (\mu_{D_{pq}}^{(r)}, \eta_{D_{pq}}^{(r)}, \nu_{D_{pq}}^{(r)})$ for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$.

The new entropy-based FUCOM-TOPSIS method for SFDMs is processed according to the following steps:

Step I: Decide the type of criteria. Determine which one is the benefit type and which one is the non-benefit type criteria. If there are any non-benefit type criteria, then the related values $d_{pq}^{(r)} = (\mu_{D_{pq}}^{(r)}, \eta_{D_{pq}}^{(r)}, \nu_{D_{pq}}^{(r)})$ for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$ attained to the SFDMs by experts should be normalized as follows:

$$s_{pq}^{(r)} = \begin{cases} d_{pq}^{(r)}, & \text{for benefit type criteria } C_q \\ (d_{pq}^{(r)})^c, & \text{for non-benefit type criteria } C_q \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$, $q = \overline{1 - m}$ and $r = \overline{1 - k}$, where $(d_{pq}^{(r)})^c$ represents the complement of $d_{pq}^{(r)}$. Hence, the spherical fuzzy normalized decision matrix (SFNDM) $D_N^{(r)} = (s_{pq}^{(r)})_{n \times m}$ where $s_{pq}^{(r)} = (\mu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)}, \eta_{s_{pq}}^{(r)}, \nu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})$ for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$ is constructed.

Step II: Calculate the weight of experts. Experts' weight can be calculated objectively using the suggested entropy measure function in a similar way given in [10]. First, we calculate the scalar value of SFNDMs by using the following equality for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$:

$$\varepsilon_{D_N^{(r)}} = -\frac{1}{\ln(mn)} \sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m \left(\frac{E(s_{pq}^{(r)})}{\sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m E(s_{pq}^{(r)})} \right) \ln \left(\frac{E(s_{pq}^{(r)})}{\sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m E(s_{pq}^{(r)})} \right) \quad (3)$$

where E is the suggested entropy measure function. Then, we compute the weight of experts (ε_r for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$) by using

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{1 - \varepsilon_{D_N^{(r)}}}{k - \sum_{r=1}^k \varepsilon_{D_N^{(r)}}}. \quad (4)$$

Step III: Establish the aggregated decision matrix. We merge the SFNDMs $D_N^{(r)}$ by considering the weight of experts (calculated in the previous step) via the SFWA operator [8] and so we obtain the spherical fuzzy aggregated decision matrix (SFADM) $D = (s_{pq})_{n \times m}$ which is constructed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} s_{pq} &= SFWA_{\varepsilon}(s_{pq}^{(1)}, s_{pq}^{(2)}, \dots, s_{pq}^{(k)}) = \bigoplus_{r=1}^k \varepsilon_r s_{pq}^{(r)} \\ &= \left(\sqrt{1 - \prod_{r=1}^k (1 - (\mu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^2)^{\varepsilon_r}}, \sqrt{\prod_{r=1}^k (1 - (\mu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^2)^{\varepsilon_r} - \prod_{r=1}^k (1 - (\mu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^2 - (\eta_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^2)^{\varepsilon_r}}, \prod_{r=1}^k (\nu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^{\varepsilon_r} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Let us denote $s_{pq} = (\mu_{A_p}(C_q), \eta_{A_p}(C_q), \nu_{A_p}(C_q))$ for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$ and $q = \overline{1 - m}$.

Step IV: Calculate the weight of the criteria objectively. The weights of the criteria can be objectively determined by using the existing entropy measure functions. Then, the criteria's weight vector, $\Omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_m)$, is computed via the subsequent equation:

$$\omega_q = \frac{1 - E(C_q)}{\sum_{q=1}^m 1 - E(C_q)}, \forall q = \overline{1 - m}. \quad (5)$$

Step V: Calculate the weight of the criteria subjectively. To calculate the weight of

criteria subjectively, we proceed FUCOM method and obtain subjective weights of the criteria $(\omega'_1, \omega'_2, \dots, \omega'_m)^T$. Next, the hybrid weight for criteria $(\Gamma = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_m))$ is computed as the following way:

$$\gamma_q = \frac{\omega_q \cdot \omega'_q}{\sum_{q=1}^m \omega_q \cdot \omega'_q}$$

for every $q = \overline{1 - m}$.

Step VI: Find the weighted aggregated decision matrix. We weight the SFADM D by considering the hybrid weight vector Γ for criteria by using the scalar multiplication on SFSs and so we construct the spherical fuzzy weighted aggregated decision matrix (SFWADM) $D' = (s'_{pq})_{n \times m}$ where s'_{pq} of D' is :

$$s'_{pq} = \left(\sqrt{1 - (1 - \mu_{A_p}(C_q)^2)^{\gamma_q}}, \sqrt{(1 - \mu_{A_p}(C_q)^2)^{\gamma_q} - (1 - \mu_{A_p}(C_q)^2 - \eta_{A_p}(C_q)^2)^{\gamma_q}}, (\nu_{A_p}(C_q))^{\gamma_q} \right) \quad (6)$$

for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$ and $q = \overline{1 - m}$. Denote $s'_{pq} = (\mu'_{A_p}(C_q), \eta'_{A_p}(C_q), \nu'_{A_p}(C_q))$.

Step VII: Determine Positive and Negative Ideal Solutions. We first transform the elements of SFWADM into real numbers by using the score function. Then the score matrix $D^* = (s^*_{pq})_{n \times m}$ is constructed where $s^*_{pq} = SF(s'_{pq}) = SF(\mu'_{A_p}(C_q), \eta'_{A_p}(C_q), \nu'_{A_p}(C_q))$ for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$ and $q = \overline{1 - m}$. Next, we calculate the Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) A^+ and Negative Ideal Solution (NIS) A^- . We'll use \mathfrak{B}_C to represent the set of benefit type criteria and \mathfrak{C}_C for non-benefit type criteria. From there, PIS A^+ and NIS A^- are determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A^+ &= \{A^+(C_1), A^+(C_2), \dots, A^+(C_m)\}, \\ A^- &= \{A^-(C_1), A^-(C_2), \dots, A^-(C_m)\} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Here,

$$A^+(C_q) = \{(max_p s^*_{pq} | C_q \in \mathfrak{B}_C), (min_p s^*_{pq} | C_q \in \mathfrak{C}_C) | 1 \leq p \leq n\}, \quad (8)$$

$$A^-(C_q) = \{(min_p s^*_{pq} | C_q \in \mathfrak{B}_C), (max_p s^*_{pq} | C_q \in \mathfrak{C}_C) | 1 \leq p \leq n\} \quad (9)$$

for every $q = \overline{1 - m}$.

Step VIII: Compute the relative closeness index and find the ranking. To compute the relative closeness index, we first find the Euclidean distance of each option A_p from the PIS and NIS.

$$\begin{aligned} d(A_p, A^+) &= \sqrt{\sum_{q=1}^m (A_p(C_q) - A^+(C_q))^2}, \\ d(A_p, A^-) &= \sqrt{\sum_{q=1}^m (A_p(C_q) - A^-(C_q))^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Then, we find the relative closeness index $(R(A_p))$ of each option A_p to measure the closeness to the PIS and furtherness to the NIS using the following equation:

$$R(A_p) = \frac{d(A_p, A^-)}{d(A_p, A^-) + d(A_p, A^+)} \quad (11)$$

for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$. Finally, the options are ranked from highest to lowest according to their relative closeness index $R(A_p)$. As a result, we consider the one with the highest ranking as the best option.

3 A Numerical Example

Now, we apply the SF-Entropy-FUCOM-TOPSIS method to evaluate digital marketing technology comprehensively ([7]), showcasing the practical applicability and efficacy of the proposed SFS-based decision-making framework. In this problem, there are three decision-makers, five alternatives and nine criteria. Details of the problem can be found in the paper [7].

The proposed SF-Entropy-FUCOM-TOPSIS method is applied to solve this problem

Step I: This step is skipped since all criteria are benefit type (or not specified).

Step II: We calculate the weight of experts by using Eq. 3 and 4 and these values are obtained as $\varepsilon_1 = 0.3379$, $\varepsilon_2 = 0.3397$, and $\varepsilon_3 = 0.3223$.

Step III: We collect the SFNDMs $D^N(r)$ given in [7] by considering the weight of experts (calculated in the previous step) via the SFWA operator and hence we find the SFADM.

Step IV: We calculate the weight of criteria objectively by using Eq. 5 and we find the weight vector

$$\Omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4, \omega_5, \omega_6, \omega_7, \omega_8, \omega_9) = (0.07, 0.11, 0.13, 0.12, 0.14, 0.11, 0.09, 0.10, 0.13).$$

Step V: We compute the weight of the criteria subjectively (according to the importance value given in [7]) by using the FUCOM method and these values are

$$\Omega' = (\omega'_1, \omega'_2, \omega'_3, \omega'_4, \omega'_5, \omega'_6, \omega'_7, \omega'_8, \omega'_9) = (0.12, 0.13, 0.15, 0.17, 0.19, 0.14, 0.12, 0.15, 0.22).$$

Then, by using objective and subjective weights, we obtain the hybrid weight for criteria weights

$$\Gamma = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3, \gamma_4, \gamma_5, \gamma_6, \gamma_7, \gamma_8, \gamma_9) = (0.05, 0.10, 0.12, 0.13, 0.16, 0.10, 0.07, 0.09, 0.18).$$

Step VI: We weight the SFADM D by considering the hybrid weight vector Γ for criteria by using scalar multiplication on SFSs. Then, we find the SFWADM.

Step VII: Then PIS A^+ and NIS A^- are found as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A^+ &= \{0.1375, 0.1356, 0.1343, 0.2076, 0.1683, 0.1654, 0.1471, 0.1437, 0.2024\}, \\ A^- &= \{0.0875, 0.0918, 0.1115, 0.1081, 0.1402, 0.0990, 0.0960, 0.1060, 0.1502\} \end{aligned}$$

Step VIII: The distances of PIS and NIS from each option A_p are calculated to determine the relative closeness index and ranking options, and they are given these values in Table 2.

Next, to emphasize the stability, robustness, and effectiveness of the proposed method, the entropy-based FUCOM-TOPSIS method, sensitive analyses are performed where the weights of experts and criteria take different values. For this purpose, the digital marketing technology problem is solved again with the proposed method using the existing entropy measures. The

Table 2: Ranking Matrix.

	$d(A, A^+)$	$d(A, A^-)$	Index	Rank
A_1	0.0993	0.0813	0.4503	3
A_2	0.1420	0.0442	0.2375	5
A_3	0.1352	0.0603	0.3084	4
A_4	0.0769	0.1204	0.6103	1
A_5	0.0854	0.1174	0.5789	2

results obtained are summarised in Table 3. As it is clear from Table 3, the best and worst options have not changed despite the different weight combinations. This shows that the proposed method provides a solid basis for decision-making and is robust to different subjective opinions.

Table 3: Results under different entropies

Entropy	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	Ranking
E_B [5]	0.45	0.24	0.31	0.61	0.58	$A_4 > A_5 > A_1 > A_3 > A_2$
E_J [9]	0.45	0.25	0.38	0.60	0.51	$A_4 > A_5 > A_1 > A_3 > A_2$
E_{AG} [2]	0.47	0.27	0.44	0.59	0.44	$A_4 > A_1 > A_3 > A_5 > A_2$

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